

TWIN PARADOX: SYMMETRY RESTORED

Vivek Krishnarao Kadwe

Independent Researcher

India

vivekkadwe.71@gmail.com

January 5, 2026

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.18153251

Abstract

Twin paradox is one of the most debated issues in the special theory of relativity. It involves two twins; one of them stays on the earth and the other travels in a spaceship away from the earth. The traveler twin returns and comes back to the earth. The paradox centers around the contention that, in relativity, either twin could regard the other as the traveler, in which case each should find the other younger – a logical contradiction.

The constancy of speed of light and the clock hypothesis play an important role in solving this contradiction. This has been done in this article in two ways. In both the ways, we arrive at a striking and novel result that after reunion of the twins, both find each other of equal age. This result is consistent with the special theory of relativity.

Keywords: Twin Paradox, Special Theory of Relativity

1 Introduction

The special theory of relativity gave rise to the famous Twin paradox. After much thought and discussions over many decades, the scientists now believe that the paradox has been successfully resolved. Almost all of them agreed that the twin who travels in a spaceship away from the earth and comes back to the earth ages less than the earth twin. The traveling twin finds himself younger than the earth twin at the end of the journey. Here I am going to give a different approach to the paradox and arrive at a new solution which is contrary to the earlier conclusions. I am going to prove that at the end of the journey, both the twins find each other of equal age and there is no asymmetric ageing involved. Constancy of the speed of light plays an important role in this proof. This solution is consistent with the special theory of relativity.

1.1 Twin Paradox

Figure 1: Astronaut twin ‘A’ and the Earth twin ‘B’. Twin A makes a high-speed space flight, then reverses direction and returns to Earth.

We begin by supposing that we have two identical twins. One of them is an astronaut. Let us call the astronaut twin ‘A’ and the earth twin ‘B’ Figure 1. A makes a space flight with high speed. After some time interval he reverses his direction of motion and comes back to earth.

As per the special theory of relativity, time dilation is a reciprocal effect. A finds B’s clock slowed down and B finds A’s clock slowed down, due to relative velocity between the two in the outward journey as well as the return journey. At the end of the journey both compare their ages. Each twin can not be younger than the other, an absurd consequence and a paradox.

2 Thought Experiments

Now we shall look at the same situation with the help of two reference frames S and S' . I shall arrive at the same result using two procedures.

2.1 Thought Experiment I

Consider a reference frame S with a light source located at origin O Figure 2. An observer stationed in S sees the wavefront of the light from O spreading as a sphere and at any moment in time t , positions in the wavefront are located by the relation in Equation 1 (ct being radius of the sphere).

$$x^2 + y^2 + z^2 = c^2t^2 \tag{1}$$

Figure 2: Wavefront as observed by two reference frames S and S' , where S' is moving with velocity v w.r.t. S in x direction

Let us assume that a second observer views the procedure from a reference frame S' which is moving parallel to x -axis of S , with velocity v . At $t = t' = 0$, both observers are at the origin O . The two frames coincided at the time when the light signal was emitted and at $t = t' = 0$. The second observer would also see the light spreading from O' as a sphere. The equation of the sphere seen in S' is given in Equation 2

$$x'^2 + y'^2 + z'^2 = c^2 t'^2 \quad (2)$$

Let us assume that, the reference frame S' reverses its direction of motion after traveling some distance. It then travels in negative x -direction. It stops when O and O' coincide again. The relative velocity between the two frames becomes zero. Now, at this point, at the end of the journey, what will be the radius of the light sphere in both the frames of reference?

At the end of the journey:-

- Both observers are at the same place.
- Both are in the same frame of reference. (Both frames now merged together.)
- There is only ONE sphere, NOT two. (ONE sphere and two reference frames merged into ONE.)

1, 2 and 3 undoubtedly proves that the radius of the sphere must be the same in both the frames of reference. The radius in both the frames is given by ct and ct' respectively. Hence, at the end of the journey, $ct = ct'$ (when O and O' coincide and when $v = 0$) Which implies $t = t'$ (c being constant). Thus, time elapsed for both observers is equal.

If the two observers are twins, one of them in S and another in S' , journey started when $t = t' = 0$, they find each other of equal age at the end of the journey also. (Since we

got, $t = t'$ at the end of the journey). I have explained acceleration and deceleration of the traveling twin later in this article.

At every instant of time, the wavefront advances with a constant velocity c in all directions with respect to O and O' . Both observers always find themselves at the centre of the sphere. At the end of the journey one and the same sphere is observed by the two observers which are stationary with respect to each other. Hence $ct = ct'$, giving the time intervals to be equal.

Let us see what happens at the end of the journey. The relative velocity v becomes zero. The reference frame S' totally coincides with S . Their co-ordinates overlap each other. In fact, S' ceases to be a different frame of reference. It merges into S . In this situation, whatever radius of light sphere is in S , the same will be in S' .

We can have another approach to the above situation as given below. If possible, suppose, $t \neq t'$ at the end of the journey, then $ct \neq ct'$. It would mean that two observers at the same place and stationary with respect to each other find the radius of the one light bubble to be unequal! Hence $ct = ct'$ at the end of the journey.

Here, I would like to explain the effect of accelerations and decelerations during the journey. **Clock hypothesis states that at any instant of time, a non-inertial frame of reference has a corresponding co-moving inertial frame of reference.** The time dilation factor and the length contraction factor of the non-inertial reference frame are equal to the respective factors of the co-moving reference frame.

- The speed of light is constant ($= c$) in all inertial reference frames.
- During period of acceleration the non-inertial reference frame will coincide with a number of **co-moving** inertial reference frames.
- For each of these inertial frames, light travels with a constant speed c .

Hence in our thought experiment the observer in S' also sees light spreading as a sphere with radius equal to the distance traveled by light. (For the observer in S' also, light traveled with a constant speed c in all directions, despite acceleration and deceleration.) The time elapsed for each observer equals the radius of the light sphere, if the speed of light is taken to be unity. The radius is the same as measured by both the observers at the end of the journey. Hence the total time elapsed for both the observers is also equal. Thus, there is no asymmetrical ageing.

2.2 Thought Experiment II

In the above experiment, instead of considering a sphere of light, we can arrive at the same result by considering only one photon. Thus, we can simplify the situation further.

Let us reconsider the situation: When the twins depart, (i.e. when $t = t' = 0$), a photon is emitted at the origin in the positive x-direction. The photon travels along the positive x-axis with the same speed c with respect to both the twins.

Figure 3: A photon as seen from 2 co-ordinate frames S and S' , where S is stationary and S' is moving with velocity v .

In the S frame, the coordinates of the photon are $(ct, 0, 0)$. Here ct is the x-coordinate of the photon. In the S' frame, the coordinates of the photon are $(ct', 0, 0)$. Here ct' is the x-coordinate of the photon. The traveler twin returns and comes back to the earth-twin. After reuniting, as seen before:

- Both twins are at the same place.
- Both are in the same reference frame. (Both frames now merged together.)

Hence, the x-coordinate of the photon with respect to both reference frames must be the same. The x-coordinates of the photon in both the frames are given by ct and ct' respectively. Hence, after reuniting, $ct = ct'$, which implies $t = t'$.

2.3 Thought Experiment III: Triplet Paradox

For the sake of support to my statements, I shall explain it with the help of one more thought experiment. Let us have triplets in place of twins – A , B and C . A and C leave earth at the same time, with the same speed, but in opposite directions. A and C perform totally symmetric journey with respect to B (who stayed on earth) and come back to earth.

Figure 4: Astronauts A and C along with the Earth person B . Astronauts A and C make a high-speed space flight in opposite directions, then reverse direction and return to Earth.

What will happen when A and C meet after completing the journey? The existing solution says:-

- A is younger than B
- C is younger than B
- Since A and C perform totally symmetric journey, we have to conclude that A and C are of equal age.

Here, have we not encountered a paradox again? Thus, the existing solution gives rise to another paradoxical situation. A and C , both are always in relative motion with respect to each other. A finds C 's clock slowed down and C finds A 's clock slowed down due to relative velocity in the outward and return journey. How is it then that both of them find each other of equal age at the end of the journey? A and B had relative velocity between them all the time, they are of different ages after meeting, but A and C also had relative velocity between them all the time, they are of same age after meeting! The existing solution can not reconcile this situation.

We quickly get the answer to this question if we resolve the twin paradox as given above in this article, apply the solution to this situation and say that all three brothers are of equal age after completion of the journey!

3 Conclusion

There is no asymmetrical ageing involved in the story of the twins. We get rid of the twin paradox (or say clock paradox) and get a simple and symmetric solution. In fact, the constancy of the speed of light with respect to all observers leads us to the consequence that both the twins are of equal age after reuniting. In the above solution, we observe that no reference frame is preferred by nature, which is consistent with the special theory of relativity. Natural laws love symmetry which is conserved in the above case also. Asymmetry is resolved and symmetry is now restored.

References

This topic is found in almost all books on special relativity. I give below only two reference books which cover the problem exhaustively. The second book is fully devoted to the twins' problem and includes a wide range of approaches and research.

- [1] Robert Resnick, *Introduction to Special Relativity*, Wiley Eastern Limited, 1968.
- [2] Leslie Marder, *Time and the space-traveller*, George Allen & Unwin Ltd., 1971.